

Evaluating the beneficial effects of the ethanol extracts of *Ocimum gratissimum* leaf in lead-induced toxicity in wistar rats

Olalekan A. Yusuf,^{1*} Al-ameen A. Mohammed,¹ Rasak A. Oyewo,² Kikelomo O. Oyeleke.³

¹Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare, Department of Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics, Faculty of Basic Clinical Sciences, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria.

²Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare, Department of Anatomy, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria.

³Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Department of Medical Laboratory Sciences, Ogbomosho, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Corresponding author: Olalekan Ahmed. Yusuf. Federal University of Health Sciences, Azare, Department of Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics, Faculty of Basic Clinical Sciences, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria. email – olalekan.yusuf@fuhhsa.edu.ng, Tel:+2347064653286

Abstract

Background: Lead (Pb) acetate is a widely encountered environmental toxicant known to cause haematological, hepatic, and reproductive impairments. *Ocimum gratissimum*, a medicinal plant rich in antioxidant and anti-inflammatory constituents, may offer protection against Pb-induced damage. This study investigated the protective effects of the ethanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* leaves on haematological indices, liver biomarkers, and fertility hormones in Pb-exposed male Wistar rats. **Materials and Methods:** Twenty-four male rats were divided into four groups (n=6): control, Pb acetate only (120 mg/kg), and two treatment groups receiving Pb acetate with *O. gratissimum* extract (125 mg/kg or 250 mg/kg) for 21 days. Haematological parameters, liver function indices, and reproductive hormones (FSH, LH, testosterone) were assessed using standard assays. Data were analysed by one-way ANOVA (p<0.05). **Results:** Pb acetate exposure significantly reduced haematological indices (WBC, RBC, Hb, PCV, MCV, MCH, MCHC) and fertility hormones, while elevating lymphocytes and liver enzymes (ALT, AST, ALP, GGT, LDH). Co-treatment with *O. gratissimum*, particularly at 250 mg/kg, markedly restored blood parameters, reduced liver enzyme activity, and normalised hormonal levels, indicating dose-dependent protective effects. **Conclusion:** Ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* leaves significantly ameliorates Pb acetate-induced haematological, hepatic, and reproductive toxicities in rats. Its protective activity is likely mediated through antioxidant and anti-inflammatory mechanisms, highlighting its therapeutic potential against heavy metal toxicity.

Keywords: Fertility hormones, Hematotoxicity, Hepaprotection, Lead intoxication, *Ocimum gratissimum*,

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ISSN: Print; 2992-555X Electronic: 3092-9865

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20668172>

Date Submitted: 3rd December 2025

Date Accepted: 2nd February 2026

Date Published Online: 10th June 2026

Cite this article as: Olalekan A. Yusuf, Al-ameen A. Mohammed, Rasak A. Oyewo, Kikelomo O. Oyeleke Evaluating the Beneficial Effects of the Ethanol Extracts of *Ocimum gratissimum* Leaf in Lead-induced Toxicity in Wistar Rats. *The Scholar J Health Scie* 2026; 2 (1): 153-162.

Introduction

Ocimum gratissimum, widely recognised as scent leaf, represents one of numerous medicinal plants demonstrating significant potential as an alternative therapeutic agent for various health conditions.¹ This perennial herbaceous plant exhibits widespread distribution and commercial viability, distinguished by its characteristic strong aromatic properties. As a member of the Lamiaceae family, *O. gratissimum* naturally occurs across Africa, Asia, and South America.² The plant is an essential dietary and culinary spice used by various ethnic groupings in Nigeria and nearby countries. Nigerian communities have established distinct local nomenclature for this plant: the Yoruba people refer to it as "efinrin," the Hausa call it "daidoya," and the Igbo know it as "nchuanwu"—representing the three predominant languages of Nigeria.³ In culinary applications, the plant functions as a natural flavouring agent, condiment, and vegetable component in preparing various dishes, including fish, meat, soups, and stews.⁴ Aside from its culinary value, *O. gratissimum* is highly valued in traditional medicine, where practitioners use it to treat a variety of health

conditions, including cough, pneumonia, fever, inflammation, anaemia, diarrhoea, pain management, and both fungal and bacterial infections.^{5,6}

Comprehensive phytochemical analysis of *O. gratissimum* has identified a diverse array of bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, phytates, oligosaccharides, and essential oils.^{7,8} Research has documented that these bioactive constituents exhibit multiple therapeutic properties, including antibacterial, antidiabetic, and antihyperlipidemic effects. Additionally, studies have demonstrated the plant's capacity to enhance haematological parameters in experimental animal models.^{9,10}

Lead (Pb) represents a persistent, nonbiodegradable toxic heavy metal capable of inducing acute and severe pathological conditions across multiple organ systems, including cardiovascular, hematological, reproductive, digestive, immunological, and neurodegenerative disorders.^{11,12} In Nigeria, occupational Pb exposure constitutes the predominant source of lead poisoning, with the most significant hazards arising from welding, printing operations, combustion processes, and copper and zinc smelting activities.^{13,14} These industrial operations pose serious health concerns not only for the workers but also for their families and the surrounding communities. The primary route of occupational lead intoxication occurs through respiratory exposure, which facilitates more rapid and complete absorption compared to percutaneous, ingestion, or transdermal pathways.¹⁵ Following absorption and systemic circulation, lead predominantly binds to red blood cells, subsequently causing damage to various organ systems. Pb exposure has been extensively linked to a spectrum of health complications, particularly haematological abnormalities, neurological dysfunction, and hepatic disorders. Pb intoxication has emerged as a critical public health concern due to its devastating effects, particularly within mining communities where exposure levels are characteristically elevated.¹⁶ The severity and widespread nature of this problem necessitate urgent intervention strategies to mitigate Pb-induced toxicity.

This study aimed to evaluate the protective effects of *O. gratissimum* against Pb acetate-induced toxicity in experimental rats. The selection of *O. gratissimum* as a potential therapeutic intervention is based on its extensive traditional use throughout Nigeria and numerous other countries for

medicinal purposes, as well as its widespread application as a culinary spice. Given this established safety profile and traditional therapeutic applications, investigating its potential benefits in Pb toxicity represents a logical and promising research direction.

Method and Materials

Chemicals

Lead acetate of 100% purity (BDH Laboratories Supplies Poole, England) was obtained from the Chemistry Department, Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. HPLC-grade methanol ($\geq 99.9\%$) was purchased from CIMAT (Riyadh, Saudi Arabia).

Plant source

Fresh *O. gratissimum* leaves were obtained from Osogbo, Osun State, and were identified and authenticated at the Department of Botany, Obafemi Awolowo University, Osun State, Nigeria, with herbarium number IFE 18286.

Plant Preparation and Extraction

Fresh *O. gratissimum* were air-dried at ambient temperature and pulverised using a mortar and pestle. The pulverised powdered (441g) sample was extracted using absolute ethanol for 72 hours. The mixture was decanted and filtered using sterile Whatman paper (3 mm) to obtain a semi-solid residue, which was further placed in a distiller. The flask was connected to the condenser and receiving flask, and the heating mantle was set to heat the mixture at a temperature of 40°C. After the condensation, the extract was poured into a sterile glass petri-dish and spread evenly for complete dryness, which was placed in a well-ventilated area at room temperature for the ethanol residue to evaporate. After the drying process, the extract was poured into a 20ml universal bottle and stored in the refrigerator. The extracts were reconstituted in water and were administered orally. The dose of OG administered was based on the result obtained from our preliminary investigation and previously reported LD50.¹⁷

Animal Care and Study Design

Twenty-four (24) adults male Wistar rats weighing 140- 275g were used for this study. The rats were obtained from Honeywell Breeder House, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria. The rats were kept in plastic cages, in a well-ventilated, disease-free animal core facility with free access to water and pellets. Ethical approval was obtained from the ethical review committee at Ladoke Akintola University, Ogbomosho, Nigeria with approval number: ERCFBMSLAUTECH 068/10/2024. The experiment was conducted in line with the

guidelines for the use of animal for experiment. Rats were acclimatized for two weeks before the commencement of Pb acetate and extract administration.

The healthy rats were randomly assigned to four (4) groups of six animals each per group: control group, received distilled water alone (0.2 mL, PO); untreated group, received lead acetate only (120 mg/kg, PO); treatment group 1, received 120 mg/kg Lead acetate and *O. gratissimum* extract (125 mg/kg, PO); and treatment group 2, received 120 mg/kg Lead acetate and *O. gratissimum* extract (250 mg/kg, PO) for twenty-one (21) days. All test compounds were administered orally once a day with the use of an oral cannula.

After 21 days of administration, rats were anaesthetised using xylazine-ketamine anaesthesia (1.25:8.75 mL, v/v). Blood samples were collected via cardiac puncture into EDTA-containing tubes. The blood was thoroughly mixed and centrifuged at 3000 x g for 10 minutes. The plasma obtained was used for hormonal fertility profile and liver biochemical markers. Liver biomarkers, including protein, albumin, bilirubin, alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, lactate dehydrogenase, and gamma-glutamyl transferase, were determined using different bioassay techniques. ELISA kits were used to quantify testosterone, FSH, and LH by following the kit protocol.

The data were expressed as Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean (SEM). The statistical significance was evaluated by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using GraphPad Prism version 8.0 (USA) with Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) option. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered to indicate a significant difference between groups.

Results

Haematological parameters of Pb acetate-induced Toxicity in Rats Treated with Ethanol Extract of *O. gratissimum* Leaves.

The haematological parameters in Pb acetate-induced toxicity in rats following treatment with ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* leaf were evaluated in this study. The oral administration of Pb acetate showed a significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in white blood cell counts, and neutrophils of all the groups except the lymphocytes, in which there is a significant increase when compared to the negative control group (Table 1). The oral administration of ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* was able to reverse the effect at all doses when compared to the negative control group (Table 1). Likewise, the administration of Pb acetate showed a significant

($P < 0.05$) decrease in anemia indices including red blood cells (RBC), packed cell volume (PCV), hemoglobin (Hb), mean cell volume (MCV), mean cell hemoglobin (MCH), and mean cell hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) of all the groups when compared to the negative control group (Table 2). The oral administration of ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* was able to reverse the effect at all doses when compared to the negative control group (Table 2).

Liver Biomarkers of Pb acetate-induced Toxicity in Rats Treated with Ethanol Extract of *O. gratissimum* Leaves.

Total proteins, albumin, and bilirubin were determined in this study to assess the effect of *O. gratissimum* on the synthetic and excretory function of the liver. The untreated group showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in the concentration of plasma total protein, albumin and bilirubin, but there was a slight increase in these biomarkers in the treated group (Figures 1 and 2).

Serum total bilirubin levels in the untreated group increased significantly compared to the control group (Figure 2A). There is a slight decrease in total bilirubin in both treatment groups (Figure 2B). Pb acetate significantly increased serum levels of ALT, AST, ALP, GGT, and LDH when compared to the control group, and the administration of ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* significantly reduced these values (Table 3).

Fertility Hormone Profile of Pb acetate-induced Toxicity in Rats Treated with Ethanol Extract of *O. gratissimum* Leaves.

Figure 3A shows the follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) levels in the plasma of the four groups. The control group and treatment groups had the highest FSH levels (2.578 \pm 0.189, 2.333 \pm 0.084, and 2.756 \pm 0.129, respectively), while the untreated group had the lowest level (1.653 \pm 0.263). Figure 3B displays the luteinising hormone (LH) levels in the presence and absence of *O. gratissimum* extracts in Pb-induced toxicity in rats. The control group showed the highest LH concentration (3.422 \pm 0.061), whereas the untreated group displayed a lower concentration (2.274 \pm 0.152). The treatment groups had intermediate LH levels, 3.129 \pm 0.234 and 3.035 \pm 0.323, respectively. Only the untreated group showed statistically significant differences when compared to the control in LH levels. Figure 3C depicts the testosterone concentrations across the experimental groups. The control had the highest testosterone level, 5.944 \pm 0.815, followed by the treatment groups, 5.139 \pm 0.467 and 5.034 \pm 0.461. The untreated group exhibited the lowest testosterone

level, 4.063 ± 0.499 , but this was not statistically significant compared to the control.

Table 1: Haematological parameters of Pb acetate-induced toxicity in Rats treated with ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* Leaves.

Groups	WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	Neutrophils (%)	Lymphocytes (%)
Control	9.50 ± 0.17^b	29.75 ± 2.06^b	70.25 ± 2.06^c
Untreated	4.65 ± 0.77^a	23.75 ± 2.39^a	76.25 ± 2.39^c
125mg/kg <i>O. gratissimum</i>	4.00 ± 0.29^a	33.50 ± 2.99^c	69.00 ± 3.56^a
250mg/kg <i>O. gratissimum</i>	9.35 ± 0.39^b	34.25 ± 2.53^c	65.75 ± 2.53^b

Values are expressed as Mean \pm S.E.M (n=4), and those with different superscripts down the column are statistically different, $p < 0.05$. WBC- white blood cells.

Table 2: Anaemia indices of Pb acetate-induced toxicity in Rats treated with ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* Leaves.

Groups	RBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	Hemoglobin (g/L)	PCV (%)	MCV (fl)	MCH (pg)	MCHC (g/dL)
Control	7.56 ± 0.27^c	15.20 ± 1.25^c	45.50 ± 1.94^c	60.12 ± 0.45^b	60.09 ± 0.12^b	33.42 ± 0.19^b
Untreated	5.16 ± 1.29^a	11.98 ± 1.26^a	25.50 ± 0.71^a	59.82 ± 0.48^a	20.29 ± 0.16^a	32.82 ± 0.07^a
125mg/kg <i>O. gratissimum</i>	7.12 ± 0.41^c	14.18 ± 1.66^b	42.75 ± 2.50^c	60.04 ± 0.66^b	60.04 ± 0.66^b	33.18 ± 0.13^b
250mg/kg <i>O. gratissimum</i>	6.56 ± 0.31^b	14.44 ± 1.13^b	34.25 ± 1.89^b	61.63 ± 1.19^b	61.63 ± 1.19^c	33.41 ± 0.20^b

Values are expressed as Mean \pm S.E.M., (n=4) and those with different superscripts down the column are statistically different, $p < 0.05$. PCV- packed cell volume, MCV- mean cell volume, MCH- mean cell haemoglobin, MCHC- mean cell haemoglobin concentration.

Figure 1. Concentrations of Serum Total Protein and Albumin in Pb acetate-induced toxicity in Rats treated with ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* Leaves.

Values are expressed as Mean \pm S.E.M., (n=4) and bars with different superscripts are statistically different, $p < 0.05$.

Figure 2. Concentrations of Serum Total and unconjugated Bilirubin in Pb acetate-induced toxicity in Rats treated with ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* Leaves.

Values are expressed as Mean \pm S.E.M., (n=4) and bars with different superscripts are statistically different, $p < 0.05$.

Table 3. Liver Enzyme Activity in Pb acetate-induced Toxicity treated with Ethanol Extract of *O. gratissimum* in Wistar rats.

Liver enzyme (UL/mg Protein)	Control	Untreated	125 mg/kg <i>O. gratissimum</i>	250 mg/kg <i>O. gratissimum</i>
ALT	15.41±2.001 ^a	22.46±2.75 ^b	15.62±0.65 ^a	16.23±0.65 ^a
AST	54.745±7.89 ^a	89.66±9.456 ^c	62.40±10.49 ^b	62.682±4.81 ^b
ALP	73.518±12.77 ^a	112.25±11.35 ^d	81.93±6.93 ^b	86.21±5.34 ^c
GGT	1.83±0.14 ^a	2.64±0.39 ^b	1.97±0.19 ^a	1.87±0.11 ^a
LDH	75.13±12.98 ^a	150.23±23.38 ^b	71.12±20.84 ^b	69.67±23.76 ^b

Values are expressed as Mean ± S.E.M., (n=4) and those with different superscripts down the row are statistically different, p<0.05. ALT - alanine amino transferase, AST - aspartate amino transferase, ALP - alkaline phosphatase, GGT - gamma glutamyl transferase, LDH - lactate dehydrogenase.

Figure 3. Protective effect of *O. gratissimum* leaf extract on fertility hormones in Lead-induced toxicity Rats. Data was expressed as Mean±SEM, n=4, *p < 0.05. control- distilled water alone, untreated- Lead acetate only.

Discussion

Haematological parameters are important indices of the physiological and pathological status of animals and humans.¹⁸ In the present study, a decrease in HB, RBC, PCV, WBC, MCV, MCHC, and MCH and elevated levels of lymphocytes were observed in the Pb acetate-treated control group (Tables 1 and 2). Reduction in HB, RBC, and PCV is probably due to the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by heavy metals, which disrupt the red blood cell membrane and its functions.¹⁹ The elevation of lymphocytes might be due to the elevated inflammatory reaction because of Pb toxicity.²⁰ In this study, the beneficial role of *O. gratissimum* on the haematological parameters is not dose-dependent; the effect of the extract at 125mg/kg slightly improved the haematological indices.

The synthetic, metabolic, and excretory functions of the liver were evaluated following oral administration of the ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* leaf in Pb acetate-induced toxicity rats. Exposure to continuous and even low Pb levels can exert liver, kidney, reproductive, and behavioural impairment. It has been proven that the liver is the most susceptible organ to Pb intoxication.²¹ The total protein is made up of various proteins, including albumin, which is specifically synthesised by the liver. In this study, there is a significant reduction in the total protein and serum albumin concentration in the untreated group (Figure 1). This may indicate acute or chronic liver damage due to the impairment in liver biosynthetic ability by Pb acetate.²² The administration of *O. gratissimum* significantly increases the serum level of both albumin and total protein (Figure 1), indicating the ameliorative effect of this plant. This is similar to the findings in other reported studies.²³

Bilirubin is a marker of hepatobiliary disease and a useful test to assess liver function and the severity of necrosis. This is because Pb acetate can cause liver cell damage, leading to an increase in bilirubin levels. Pb acetate caused hepatocellular lesions and destruction of the bile duct; consequently, cell membranes are damaged, and serum liver enzymes are elevated. Furthermore, bilirubin was released into the bloodstream due to hepatocyte destruction. This causes an increase in the level of bilirubin in the blood circulation. The decrease in bilirubin observed in this study suggests that *O. gratissimum* extract ameliorates Pb acetate-induced hepatotoxicity.

ALT, AST, ALP, GGT, and LDH are enzymes found in high concentrations in the liver; thus, elevation of these enzymes may be a valuable biomarker of liver injury.²⁴ Elevation of these enzymes in serum may be partly due to the disruption of hepatocytes' membrane integrity and leakage of these enzymes into the systemic circulation.²⁵ Therefore, impairment of cell membrane integrity of hepatocytes and leakage of transaminases, ALP, GGT and LDH in the serum in this study may be due to free radical interaction with the membrane's lipids, especially phospholipids. Previous studies have explained that lead toxicity is associated with liver damage. The restoration of ALT, AST, ALP, GGT, and LDH activities to near normal levels by the extracts indicates that *O. gratissimum* has protective effects against Pb acetate. These findings could be attributed to the bioactive compounds present in *O. gratissimum*, capable of stabilising the cell membrane, preventing enzyme leakage, restoring hepatocytes, and regenerating hepatic parenchyma.²⁶

Pb acetate is a known environmental toxicant that disrupts the activity of the hypothalamic-pituitary-

gonadal axis, which is central to fertility.²⁷ This metal could be deposited in any of these glands, resulting in a hormonal imbalance. For instance, disruption of the structural architecture of the hypothalamic tract may lead to a reduction in the release of gonadotropin-releasing hormone from the hypothalamus with consequent effect on the pituitary gland and the gonads.²⁸ A reduction in FSH and LH levels will affect testosterone production and spermiogenesis.²⁹ Consequently, there will be reproductive problems that may lead to male infertility. In this study, the concentrations of the three major male hormones, FSH, LH, and testosterone, were significantly reduced in the Pb acetate group, suggesting the toxic effect of this metal on the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis. The administration of leaf extract of *O. gratissimum* with Pb acetate revealed a protective effect of the extract on the pituitary gland, with an increase in FSH, LH and testosterone levels compared to the Pb acetate group. This suggests that this extract can ameliorate or prevent the disruptive effect of Pb acetate on the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis.

Conclusion

These effects seen with this extract may be due to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory pharmacologic activity. The administration of *O. gratissimum* extracts shows promise in preventing the toxic effects of Pb acetate on reproductive and liver functions, as well as the blood. The extract shows benefits even at a lower concentration. Since *O. gratissimum* is widely used as a spice and condiment in many communities, especially around Pb mines, the plant can be explored as a nutraceutical to prevent Pb-induced toxicities.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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